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D5.4 - Final report on EPOS-Private Sector interaction

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Leader Partner	IG PAS
Main Author(s)	Stanisław Lasocki, Beata Orlecka-Sikora, Anna Leśnodorska
Contributing author(s)	-
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Table of content

Executive Summary.....	3
1. Introduction	3
2. Methodology and data used to work out the strategy for EPOS RI – PS interaction	5
3. Specific EPOS conditions for interaction with the private sector.....	7
PS as an EPOS user.	7
PS as an EPOS supplier	8
PS as an EPOS partner	9
4. Recommendation for the strategy for EPOS-Private Sector interaction.....	9
Appendix 1 - Main recommendations from ESFRI [ESFRI Scripta Vol. 2: Long-Term Sustainability of Research Infrastructures 2017]	19

Task Leader: IG PAS; Participants: ETHZ, GFZ, LTU, IMO

Revised strategy for EPOS-Private Sector interaction and provided by task 5.1, 5.3 and 5.4.

Executive Summary

This document contains the revised strategy for EPOS-Private Sector interaction and is provided by tasks 5.1, 5.3, and 5.4. The authors present a recommended strategy for interaction between EPOS and the private sector (PS), including the industry and SMEs, Chapter 2 describes the methodology used to explore the structure of the relationship between EPOS and the PS and to propose strategic initiatives for efficient interaction with PS to develop innovation is based on the key strategic actions within the EPOS SP project. In Chapter 3 authors analysed cooperation with Private Sector from three different perspectives: user, supplier, and partner. In Chapter 4 there are recommendations for the strategy for EPOS-Private Sector interaction, together with recommended actions to be taken at the operational level for the implementation, in part or in whole, of the recommendations.

1. Introduction

The subject of the current deliverable is the recommended strategy for interaction between EPOS and the private sector (PS), including the industry and SMEs. **The term “Private Sector (PS)” used here encompasses the industry, SMEs but also individuals or groups of individuals that work as experts for the industry.** The work of experts for industrial companies can be in any organizational form, such as provided by consulting enterprises or as subcontracted work by individuals employed elsewhere, e.g., from academia, et al.

“EPOS, the European Plate Observing System, is a multidisciplinary, distributed research infrastructure that facilitates the integrated use of data, data products, and facilities from the solid Earth science community in Europe” (www.epos-eu.org/about-epos). EPOS is the flagship research infrastructure in Solid Earth sciences. In 2023 EPOS will enter an operational phase.

Whereas EPOS as a research infrastructure is primarily intended for users from the science sector, users from non-science sectors, in particular from the private sector (PS), including industry, are expected and warmly welcomed. This is due to the awareness that the further development and competitiveness of EPOS significantly depend on its activity for innovation in Europe. The Communication on a new European Research Area for Research and Innovation, adopted by the European Commission on 30 September 2020, with a view to European Partnerships distinctly declares “European R&I partnerships, with Member States and industry, in key policy areas are seen

to be essential for prioritizing investments and reforms in research and innovation towards the green and digital transition and to support Europe's economic recovery." The indicated key policy areas are: health, accessibility, digital, industrial competitiveness, climate, energy, mobility, natural resources and food systems.

In the document "Innovation-oriented cooperation of Research Infrastructures" (ESFRI Scripta, vol. 3, Jan. 2018) ESFRI Innovation Working Group distinguished two models of the relationship between research infrastructure (RI) and industry. In the downstream business model, the industry is a user of RI. In the upstream business model, the industry is a RI's supplier. EPOS adopts this distinction for its interaction with the PS. Furthermore, EPOS also considers the possibility that any of these two types of interactions can be raised at the higher level of a synergistic partnership of EPOS with stakeholders from PS¹. Therefore, the recommendations given in the current deliverable take into account, where necessary, the role of PS as an EPOS user, supplier or partner.

The importance of cooperation between EPOS and PS was emphasized by inserting this issue as one of the key objectives of the EPOS SP project, to jointly ensure the long-term sustainability of the EPOS infrastructure. The problem has been forwarded for consideration in a separate WP5 package "Strengthening Links with Private Sector" of the EPOS SP project.

The objectives of WP5 have been:

- to increase EPOS the visibility and attractiveness for industry and SMEs;
- to improve the visibility of the EPOS innovation potential;
- to prepare legal, organizational, financial, technical, and ethical frameworks for enhancing cooperation with the private sector, with special attention dedicated to innovation-driven frameworks for the EPOS-industry partnership.

with the following four tasks to achieve these goals:

- T1 Pilot Areas for EPOS collaboration with the private sector
- T2 EPOS interactions with EU Private Sector
- T3 Development of the legal and organizational setting for EPOS-industry cooperation
- T4 Creation of EPOS Research and Innovation Services (RIS).

The current deliverable is a result of the works in the framework of T2. However, it is based on the results from other tasks as well as other materials.

This document is structured as follows. The methodology and data used to work out the strategy for EPOS RI - PS interaction is given in Section 2. Section 3 discusses specific EPOS conditions for this interaction. The implications of these conditions for the prepared recommendations are also analysed there. Finally, the resulting recommendations are presented in Section 4.

¹ In EPOS documentation (i.e., <https://www.epos-eu.org/who-benefits/industry>), an industrial stakeholder at this cooperative level of interaction is called a customer. This name does not seem to be appropriate in the context used, so we change it to 'partner.'

2. Methodology and data used to work out the strategy for EPOS RI – PS interaction

The methodology used to explore the structure of the relationship between EPOS and the PS and to propose strategic initiatives for efficient interaction with PS to develop innovation is based on the key strategic actions within the EPOS SP project. These actions are Action 2 - “Technical Sustainability and Innovation”, Action 3 - “Establish and Maintain Excellence”, and Action 4 - “Exploit Economic and Societal Benefits”. These actions are related to key activities dedicated to increasing EPOS visibility and attractiveness for the PS by disseminating the EPOS innovation potential.

These key activities are:

1. The use of pilot areas to emphasize and test the EPOS readiness and landscapes for collaborating with PS. The following pilot areas have been developed within the EPOS SP project: (i) private sector uptake and use of strong ground motion services from EPOS Seismology, (ii) anthropogenic hazard: strengthening service provision for geo-resources, (iii) volcanic plume model application to design services for the aviation community, and (iv) physical access to research infrastructures – a common interest for the private sector and EPOS;
2. Activities to map the EPOS interactions with the private sector;
3. Development of the legal and organizational setting for EPOS-PS cooperation;
4. Technical recommendations for ICS-C service improvement for facilitating the collaboration with PS and for the EPOS Research and Innovation Services (RIS).

The above activities are described in detail in the deliverables of Work Package 5 of EPOS SP:

1. D5.1 Report on pilots dedicated to The Private Sector,
2. D5.2 First Report on EPOS-Private Sector interaction,
3. D5.3 Second Report on EPOS-Private Sector interaction,
4. D5.5 Overview of the legal regulations for EPOS-Private Sector collaboration,
5. D5.6 First Report on legal and organizational regulations for EPOS-Private Sector interactions,
6. D5.7 Final Report on legal and organizational regulations for EPOS-Private Sector interactions,
7. D5.8 Plan for the sustainability of EPOS utilizing the ICS
8. D5.9 Report on the sustainability of EPOS utilizing the ICS.

During the implementation of the WP5 plan, the information on the EPOS – PS interactions and EPOS innovation potential has been collected from both desktop analysis, direct engagement with stakeholders from different pilot areas, EPOS Thematic Core Services having the potential of cooperating with the PS and other entities working in the innovation ecosystem. The latter were:

- Innovation Advisory Committee of Thematic Core Service Anthropogenic Hazards,
- Research and Technology Organizations: POLE AVENIA, TWI,
- Academia,

- Companies,
- The innovation and private sector-oriented associations like the American Rock Mechanics Association, Eurocontrol, ISAVIA (Air Service Navigation Provider of Iceland), Icelandair, Rolls Royce, ENAV (Air Service Navigation Provider of Italy), the German Airline Pilot's Association
- The ENRIITC project outcomes
- Common workshops of WP5 and the ENRIITC project
- Contacts with the Industry Liaison Officer of the European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN) and F4E - Fusion for Energy Research Infrastructures, involved in the European Spallation Source ERIC
- Personal experience of members of WP5 gained during long-lasting collaboration with the PS.

The Horizon 2020 ENRIITC project (H2020 INFRAINNOV-02-2019, Grant Agreement Number: 871112) aims to build a permanent pan-European network of Industrial Liaison and Contact Officers (ILOs and ICOs) and enable the industry to become a full partner of research infrastructures (RIs). Through its activities by supporting ILOs and ICOs, ENRIITC is helping to support the establishment of strategic, cross-border partnerships between the industry and RIs. One of the outputs of this project are the strategic recommendations for improved interactions between RIs and companies on the topic of innovation, reported as D2.1 ("Report on the mapping of the industry as a supplier and user"), and selected input from other studies. The work proposes an overall strategy to improve the engagement between European RIs and industry and forms the recommendations on strategy for innovation presented in the deliverable D3.2 ("Strategy for innovation and industry-RI cooperation"). The recommendations for the RIs-industry cooperation have been worked out based on the experiences of 51 ICOs or RI staff responsible for industry collaborations representing various RIs in Europe. The respondents represented 44 different institutions active in a variety of scientific disciplines. 76% of the RIs were on the ESFRI Roadmap 2018 either as Landmarks (56%) or Projects (36%). The research domain of Physical Sciences and Engineering was most strongly represented (33%), while the Environmental domain was represented by 12% of respondents. Nearly two-thirds of the surveyed RIs (65%) were distributed facilities, with the remainder (35%) being single-sited. The results of the ENRIITC project are relevant for EPOS, and during the common workshop, it was discussed how to adapt these results to EPOS RI in the most efficient way. Finally, the recommendations for efficient EPOS – the Private Sector interactions have been developed based on:

- ENRIITC Deliverable 2.1. "ENRIITC Report on the Mapping of Industry as RI-supplier and RI-user", Nikolaj Zangenberg (DTI), Nigel Wagstaff (EATRIS), Sylwia Wójtowicz (WPT), Javier Echavarri Delmas (CDTI), Ilaria Nardello (SZN), Gerard Cornet (NWO), Franciska De Jong (CLARIN), John Picard (EMSO).
- ENRIITC Deliverable 3.1. "Strategy to exploit the innovation potential of RIs", Marco Galeotti/EMSO, Nikolaj Zangenberg/DTI, Peter Frank/DTI, Ed Mitchel/ESRF, SZN, CDTI.

- ENRIITC Deliverable 3.2. “Strategy for innovation and industry-RI cooperation”, Nikolaj Zangenberg/DTI, Marco Galeotti/EMSO, Peter Frank/DTI, Ilaria Nardello/SZN, Javier Echávarri Delmás/CDTI, Sylwia Wojtowicz/WPT, Ana Belen/CDTI, Franciska de Jong/CLARIN, Gerard Cornet/NWO.

We also benefited from the outcomes of the ENVRIplus project. The ENVRI is a community of Environmental Research Infrastructures, projects, networks and other diverse stakeholders interested in environmental Research Infrastructure matters. The community also includes e-infrastructures supporting the Research Infrastructures in data solutions. “ENVRIplus – Supporting environmental research with integrated solutions” is a Horizon 2020 project, implemented in the period 2015-2019, which brought together Environmental and Earth System Research Infrastructures, projects and networks together with technical specialist partners to create a more coherent, interdisciplinary and interoperable cluster of Environmental Research Infrastructures across Europe. For the purpose of the EPOS-PS interaction strategy we used ENVRIplus Deliverable 18.5. “RI Innovation And Industry Liaison Preparedness Roadmap”, John Picard, Vito Vitale.

3. Specific EPOS conditions for interaction with the private sector

“EPOS, the European Plate Observing System, is a multidisciplinary, distributed research infrastructure that facilitates the integrated use of data, data products, and facilities from the solid Earth science community in Europe”. The given definition of EPOS shapes the recommendations on the strategy of interaction between EPOS and the private sector (the PS). However, they have to take be adjusted to the role of the PS, whether a user or supplier.

PS as an EPOS user.

The major value of EPOS relies in that it is a multidisciplinary infrastructure. This multidisciplinary aspect can be of paramount interest of users from PS. Distributed interactions between the PS and particular EPOS Thematic Core Services, institutions that are members of particular TCS consortia, and individual scientists from the EPOS community are, in general, important. However, first of all, efforts should be made to encourage the private sector to take advantage of EPOS's multidisciplinary offering. The reasons for this are as follows: First, as highlighted above, EPOS is "a multidisciplinary research infrastructure". EPOS is not a federation of "the community-specific integrated infrastructures", which are TCS-s. Second, the gathered information indicates that the interest of PS in the community-specific integrated infrastructures is generally low. Required data is either already accessible through sources different from EPOS, or, for larger enterprises, the data is collected in-house, or it is gathered by contracted institutions. In the two latter instances, the data can satisfy specific requirements of PS, which is not the case of EPOS data. Similarly, when community-specific services, tailored for PS needs are in mind, they are provided either by companies' R&D units or by contracted specialized institutions. The PS is in general, satisfied with the current type of interactions with (academic) organizations which, even when are members of

TCS consortia, develop their contacts on their own, not through EPOS. Contrary to that, apart from EPOS as a whole, there are few sources (if any) of multidisciplinary data and services in the solid Earth domain.

Therefore, the main question posed regarding the interactions between EPOS and the PS as a user is: How to interest the PS, industry in particular, in the use of multidisciplinary infrastructures (DDSS-s available from ICS-C, tailored IT facilities, i.e., ICS-D-s) integrated into EPOS? It is clear that the primary role in developing EPOS-PS interaction has EPOS-ERIC. But the participation of TCSs in this task is also essential as the TCS-s possess the knowledge about industrial organizations that can become users of multidisciplinary EPOS offerings.

As indicated, the use of community-specific data from EPOS (a particular TCS data) by the PS is not and will not be dominant though it is not excluded too. Furthermore, there are also other services of EPOS TCS-s, institutions – members of TCS consortia, and individuals from TCS-s that can be valuable to the industry. These could be, e.g., specialized training, tailored services, expert opinions, etc. These kinds of activities are not the primary scope of the strategy for EPOS, understood as a multidisciplinary infrastructure. But EPOS is also a community of European scientists recognizing the value and working to integrate solid Earth science research infrastructures. EPOS as a whole may benefit from the mentioned distributed provisions to the PS and, therefore should support them.

PS as an EPOS supplier

In this case, the situation is entirely different than in the case of PS as a user. A skeleton of the EPOS Delivery Framework is the TCS-ICS federated system. The Thematic Core Services (TCS-s) are community-specific integration. Consequently, with the exception of IT services and soft services (legal, promotional, etc.) directed to the whole EPOS, EPOS supply is a community-specific supply and is significantly diverse. Therefore, EPOS interactions with suppliers take place at the level of TCS or national organizations whose research infrastructures contribute to EPOS. The mentioned exceptional services provided to the EPOS-ERIC level, if provided by the PS, are easy to contract and do not need a particular strategy for their development.

The supply of goods and services to EPOS components (TCS-s, member organizations) can be either commercial (more often) or non-commercial (in rare cases). When it is on a commercial basis, it can take place only at the level of legal entities. This means that if it concerns a community-specific supply, it takes place at the level of organization/institutions from EPOS TCS consortia, not at the TCS-s level because TCS-s are not legal entities.

Charge-free supply of PS (Industry)-owned data and services going directly for integration in TCS-s is unlike but not impossible. TCS AH has repeatedly broken the barrier of distrust and persuaded industrial organizations to contribute data free of charge. However, this used to be after the data had lost its commercial value. The industry will not provide EPOS the recent data. For this and other TCS-specific reasons, the charge-free supply of PS data to the TCS-s, other than the TCS AH, may be more complex and less possible.

When the PS is an EPOS supplier, TCS consortia members have the primary role, and if it is a non-commercial supply, along with TCS coordinators. The role of EPOS-ERIC should be supportive.

PS as an EPOS partner

The EPOS-PS interaction can be elevated to a partnership level both when the PS is an EPOS user, as it is an EPOS provider, and as it has both roles. The partner appreciates the value of integrating research infrastructures into EPOS and actively and continuously interacts with the institutions and individuals in EPOS for the maintenance and further development of EPOS. At the same time, it benefits from the joint development of EPOS value for innovation.

With this understanding of partnership, it can be realized through a wide variety of activities, impossible to detail here. Whether an interaction is a partnership or not is determined by the relationship between the PS and EPOS, not what activity binds this partnership together.

At the same time, it follows from such an understanding of partnership that it is the most difficult level of interaction to achieve. The PS has precisely defined goals for its activities. They rarely include disinterested support of science, and if they do, the channels of support have already been worked out. Only cooperation with the private sector in the field of stimulating innovation seems to offer a chance for the development of partnerships EPOS - representatives of the PS.

4. Recommendation for the strategy for EPOS-Private Sector interaction

1. **Encouraging the Private Sector to take an interest in EPOS as a multidisciplinary integrated infrastructure.** It is recommended that use cases demonstrating the commercial use of EPOS multidisciplinary and the success stories describing such successful commercial use be worked out and then promoted. Such activities carried out at the EPOS-ERIC and ICS-C levels should be supported by a mandatory bottom-up flow of information from TCSs about potential PS users and suppliers.
2. **EPOS open to a commercial user.** The entire integrated EPOS infrastructure should have a CC: BY license. A private sector user must feel safe using the multidisciplinary EPOS content. Users will not analyse the licenses of individual infrastructures. Encountering a CC: BY-NC type license will discourage a PS user from using EPOS.
3. **Monitor the use of EPOS by private sector users and make the monitoring results public.** There will be several benefits of such monitoring. First, making public information about EPOS users from the PS will have a positive impact on increasing private sector interest in EPOS and increasing the number of EPOS users from the PS. It is even possible to create a snowball effect among potential EPOS users from the PS. Second, it will document to potential suppliers from the PS the value of EPOS to the private sector and thus encourage the private sector to interact with EPOS as suppliers. Finally, it will document the private sector's interest in EPOS, which can be presented at any concerned forum. User registration

at the ICS-C level is recommended. Transitionally, this could be a registration of users' affiliations only or, ultimately, an answer to the question of provenance - whether from PS or not.

4. **Support for distributed, TCS-led interaction with the PS.** It is recommended that such interactions be supported centrally, at the EPOS-ERIC level, by disseminating to the PS information not only about EPOS as a whole but also about the specifics of individual TCSs and EPOS communities. At this level, it would also be worthwhile to broker the services provided by individual TCSs. It should be incumbent on the TCSs to prepare appropriate information and promotional materials for the aforementioned centrally conducted support activities. In particular, TCSs should be required to prepare use cases and success stories showing the commercial use of the community-specific infrastructures integrated into TCS-s. It is also recommended that TCS-s be required to report annually on their collaboration with the PS. Since not all TCSs may develop cooperation with the PS, the report could inform on the lack of cooperation provided that the reasons are explained at the same time. Such an obligation could be formally mandated as a separate and compulsory item in the Multiyear Collaboration Agreements on Governance and Coordination.
5. **Interaction with PS as a supplier.** It is recommended to centrally, from the EPOS-ERIC level, support the development of interaction between TCSs and private sector suppliers by promoting in the PS the value of EPOS to society so as to interest the PS in enriching EPOS. It is advisable to consider the option of inter-TCS coordination of commercial acquisition of goods and services, etc. Also, EPOS-ERIC could sign framework agreements with suppliers from the PS.
6. **Research and Innovation service.** Elevating the EPOS-PS interaction to the level of partnership will be served by the EPOS community's display of innovative solutions or at least have the potential for innovation. It is recommended to build a separate Research and Innovation (R&I) service in ICS-C, where researchers would post solutions with innovation potential. Such a service would be a technical brokerage tool. Consideration could be given to allowing the posting of solutions with innovation potential in the R&I service also by individuals and groups outside the EPOS community. Adoption of such a rule would expand the influence of EPOS in both the scientific and industrial communities. In time, the use of R&S service by the supplier from outside EPOS could also be commercialized.
7. **ICS-Innovation (ICS-I).** Whereas ICS-D extends the ICS-C in a virtualized way with additional computing facilities to support workflows, processing, or visualization functionalities², a newly-built ICS-I would extend the ICS-C with a facility gathering EPOS solutions ready-to-use by the PS. In addition to its primary function of presenting EPOS solutions to industry

² /www.epos-eu.org/integrated-core-services

customers, ICS-I would be helpful to monitor the interest in EPOS of stakeholders from the PS and changes in this interest. Commercialization around ICS-C was also a possibility.

8. **Networking with industry research and technological organizations** is strongly recommended.

It is recommended that the following actions be taken at the operational level for the implementation, in part or in whole, of the above recommendations.

1. **Creation of a permanent structure in the governance of EPOS to facilitate interactions with the private sector. This can be accomplished by employing a full-time contact point for the industry - an Industry Contact Officer (ICO) established on the level of EPOS ERIC.**

The role of ICO is defined as a function or person employed in the research infrastructure (RI) to work with the relations with the private sector, and it plays a key role in the development and implementation of the strategy for interaction with the private sector. The definition and the responsibilities of ICO may be found in ENRIITC D3.3 “Strategy for the training of ILOs/ICOs and outreach towards industry”.

EPOS is a multidisciplinary, distributed research infrastructure. For such a distributed facility, it may be a challenge to collaborate and share knowledge regarding industrial users of the services from EPOS. One of the significant problems observed during the WP5 execution is the fragmentation of the dialogue due to the lack of an entity/person to sustain the dialogue between the dispersed meetings of those involved in substantive work within the TCSs. The lack of continuity combined with the considerable spatial dispersion of those involved in the work of the TCSs results in a lack of space to gather consistent and continuous information and conclusions on relevant aspects of cooperation with the private sector. The role of the TCS is prominent, as they treasure the knowledge and will ultimately interact with the private sector directly through their members. Thus, the ICO cannot work solely at the EPOS ERIC level without interactions with TCSs. The ICO must maintain close contact with the persons at the TCS level or partners of TCSs engaged with the industry. This is necessary to document RI’s societal impact and find best practices and examples of the industrial usage of the RI that may inspire other companies to engage. Therefore, **we recommend that TCSs contribute to EPOS ERIC requests on interactions with the private sector through a regulated activity in the Multiyear Collaboration Agreement for Governance and Coordination.**

The main objectives for the activity of ICO should be:

- a. Promoting cooperation with the private sector that is geared towards stimulating innovation;

- b. Creating cooperation with the private sector to support the sustainability of the integrated infrastructure;
- c. Developing a strategy for innovation with the private sector. The strategy process aims to collect information and formulate the ambitions of the RI in this area. Recommendations from ENRIITC's experience when formulating the RI strategy for industry engagement towards innovation are: (i) An industry strategy should start from a knowledge of the primary interest of the industry – suppliers, users, co-developers and/or tech-transfer partners; (ii) The strategy should include relevant KPIs that may easily be collected so that the progress may be monitored; (iv) The strategy should be clear on the benefits for both the RI and the companies (and other stakeholders); (v) The internal stakeholders relevant to the execution of the strategy must also be identified by answering the following: who should contribute to the strategy? who approves and “owns” the strategy? how is the follow-up process for the strategy? And how are TCSs engaged? (vi) A strategy for industry engagement cannot only rely on an inside-out approach (i.e., one that only focuses on the RI and the strengths and offers), it should be tested with the relevant companies from either supplier, users or collaborators (or/and Industry Advisory Board) and Industry Liaison Officers' networks; (vii) The strategy must be discussed and, potentially, revised at least once a year.
- d. Introducing structured methods for describing the infrastructure collected within EPOS ERIC in a way that facilitates the regulation of cooperation with the private sector. The following aspects should be taken into account: (i) the ownership structure of the infrastructure; (ii) the basic characteristics of the collected infrastructure; (iii) the type of services provided; (iv) the legal instruments implemented (type of licenses, etc.). Gathering this information in one place and structuring it according to common rules will not only facilitate the creation of an advanced legal framework but will also be an important knowledge base for private parties interested in cooperation.
- e. Mapping of information on existing cooperation with the private sector in all TCSs with information on legal solutions adopted. A structured description of existing relationships can form the basis for sharing/copying or correcting existing practices and exploring sources of innovation-based partnerships.
- f. Recommending technical and communication solutions aimed at obtaining up-to-date information on the interest of the private sector in the services offered in TCSs. Knowing the real current interest can help to develop services, adapt legal tools and work on specific collaborative offers based on innovation.
- g. Creating a database of use cases (success stories) of cooperation with the private sector, including innovative projects. Structured, centrally accessible information will allow learning by example and the search for general solutions for the future.

2. Establishing an Innovation Advisory Board for the EPOS ERIC.

An Innovation Advisory Board (IAB) with industrial representation provides broader expertise in light of new opportunities within research and innovation. IAB may assess the ideas and initiatives for interaction with PS. This feedback may be collected ad-hoc from individual companies, via events or through collaboration with project consortia, industry associations, and ILOs networks. The board may also advise on (i) the content and priorities of EPOS ERIC strategy for interaction with PS and innovation; (ii) on engaging with innovation activities and new approaches to delivering innovation within EPOS; (iii) EPOS's participation in the research and innovation undertakings; (iv) how EPOS can capitalise on its expertise and experience in collaboration with PS and innovation; (v) how EPOS's interaction with PS and EPOS's contribution to innovation can best be promoted to stakeholders and government representatives; (vi) approaches to capturing, measuring and communicating the impact derived from collaboration with PS and innovation activities supported by EPOS.

3. Incorporation requirements of the interactions of EPOS - the private sector into the communication strategy for EPOS.

Research infrastructures require close interaction with different stakeholders to provide data, data products, and services on demand, inform about their activities, engage users, founders, etc. Strategic internal and external communication is key to achieving the objectives of any research infrastructure. We recommend creating/customizing the EPOS ERIC communication strategy to the aims of the strategy of EPOS-PS interaction. This requires tailored actions and tools that should be considered during the process of developing and implementing a communication strategy taking into account specific structures and requirements of PS and research infrastructures. An EPOS ERIC communication strategy needs to be supplemented with a communication plan for PS defining specific actions and activities to achieve the aims set out in the communication strategy and EPOS-PS interaction strategy. The EPOS ERIC communication plan needs to focus on strengthening awareness of the potential benefits of a partnership between EPOS RI and the private sector. Efforts to gain the interest of the private sector should focus on (i) targeting users that may be interested in multidisciplinary integrated data/data products and services; (ii) identifying success stories and especially building use cases focusing on multidisciplinary integrated data; (iii) reflecting on the EPOS offer to industry related to reducing environmental impact; (iv) defining the position of EPOS when it comes to working with industry as a partner, or when the private sector is an indirect user (e.g. through scientists acting as consultants); (v) defining the capacity of EPOS to offer services for open innovation. The activities should include collaboration with field intermediaries (Industry Liaison Officers, Knowledge and Innovation Communities, and Industrial Associations). We recommend the creation of dedicated communication channels that will help EPOS to develop more efficient relationships with the private sector. One of the ideas is included in this document as a recommendation (R&D services). Still, the others may be found in the

outcomes of the ENRIITC project in Deliverable 3.4, “Practical Step-by-step guide for ILOs and ICOs to organise brokerage events” – a step-by-step guide on the practice of organising events with companies, and Deliverable 5.1, “ENRIITC Website lunch” – description of the website providing an online space for sharing information and opportunities for stakeholders.

We recommend to consider employing an EPOS ERIC communication officer with commercial promotion experience and skills.

4. Developing the initial strategy for innovation and adopting the Innovation Preparedness Roadmap from ENVRIplus (ENRIITC Deliverable 3.1, ENVRIplus Deliverable 18.5).

EPOS ERIC needs an initial strategy for innovation to be able to specify the strategic directions of the RI toward the stakeholders. As a starting point for discussing strategic actions for innovation, we recommend, after the ENRIITC project, implementing the “Research Infrastructures Innovation-Preparedness Roadmap” developed within the ENVRIplus project. This tool was developed for RIs to help to improve the RI internal structure to follow the ESFRI vision for sustainable RI (Appendix 1). “Research Infrastructures Innovation Preparedness Roadmap” helps to exploit the innovation potential of RI. It helps to create an efficient knowledge base that will support industrial innovation and Open Innovation models between RIs. The Open Innovation concept is an important idea for making knowledge available across European institutions. Much knowledge is assembled at the individual RIs, and the free circulation of researchers and knowledge would lead to better cross-border cooperation building of critical mass and continent-wide competition (ENRIITC Deliv. 3.1).

The roadmap is composed of five main actions:

- a. Establish a pan-European ICO and ILO network to provide advice and support to all RIs in their engagement with the industry, drawing upon existing experience and good practice and building its body of knowledge as the hub matures.
- b. Adopt a set of core competencies for ICOs and ILOs. The role of ILO and ICO is defined, including duties and competencies. It is recommended that each RI appoints an ICO. EPOS RI should review and implement specific key actions; the most important of them are mentioned above.
- c. Review and implement specific key actions proposed in this document as recommendations to help the EPOS RI improve its collaboration with the industry.
- d. Building strategic alliance relationships. Establishing partnerships at the European level to ensure that the RI operational model and interaction modes with the industry are understood and recognised so that RIs may reach more easily individual collaboration partners. Some examples are provided in the recommendation no 5.

- e. Develop EPOS RI Innovation Strategy to describe the ambitions for better integration between RIs and industry. The strategy will enable RIs to be the core engine of the innovation supply chain facilitating the constituency of spin-offs, start-ups and partnerships with private entities in close cooperation with universities.

5. Engaging the innovation ecosystem

The Innovation Preparedness Roadmap will help to form an initial strategy for specifying the strategic directions towards the stakeholders. It will also help to understand the role RI wants to take and to set up formal contacts with the associations and organizations from the innovation ecosystem. It is crucial to ensure that the EPOS RI operational model and interaction modes with industry are understood and recognised at a European level. Following the ENRIITC project experiences, we recommend formally setting the link with the European structures: (i) The European Institute of Innovation and Technologies (EIT, <https://eit.europa.eu>) Knowledge & Innovation Communities (KICS) for cooperation on joint Entrepreneurship Training programmes and industry-partnering event organisation. EPOS may exploit the MoU signed by EIT and the Board of European Environmental Research Infrastructures (BEERI); (ii) The PERIIA Network (<http://periiia.squarespace.com>), which has the aim of paving the way and preparing for the initiation of the Pan-European RI ILO Association as a formal European association; (iii) EIROFORUM (<http://eiroforum.org>), which is the forum for policy coordinating and lobbying between 8 Big Science organisations; (iv) The EOSC Digital Innovation Hub (DIH, <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services>), international and multi-partner cooperation that supports companies in easily accessing the digital technologies and services offered by EOSC.

We encourage EPOS ERIC also to develop links with PS via:

- a. Industry Association and Interest Group Aggregators: Pan-EU and national industry federations and associations, industry lobby and interest groups that actively follow and advise on socio-economic issues and technology developments on behalf of PS members and stakeholders. Below are the most relevant aggregator organisations in the environmental domain which could be interesting for EPOS:

EUROPEAN SPACE INDUSTRIES ASSOCIATION – EUROSPACE; Industry sector: ICT, SPACE

Eurospace is the trade association of the European Space Industry. Eurospace member companies represent 90% of the total turnover of the European Space Industry. Eurospace members are the main European space systems manufacturers and launch services providers. They range from large satellite systems integrators to smaller equipment manufacturers, small systems manufacturers, service operators to launch systems architect

and launcher elements manufacturers or engineering and software services. The Eurospace membership covers 14 European countries. *BLUE MINING DEEP SEA MINING CONSORTIUM*; *Industry sectors: MINING, MARINE*

Blue Mining is a European international partnership of 19 industry and research organisations on various maritime fields of expertise focused on developing solutions that will bring sustainable deep-sea mining a big step closer. The Blue Mining consortium addresses all aspects of the deep-sea mining value chain, from resource discovery to resource assessment and from exploitation technologies to the legal and regulatory framework.

EUROPEAN NON-FERROUS METALS ASSOCIATION – EUROMETAUX; *Industry sectors: METALS, RAW MATERIALS*

Brussels-based Eurometaux's, the European Non-Ferrous Metals Industries Association, priority policy areas are climate change and energy policy – the impact of the enforcement of EU climate change policy; security of raw materials supplies: EU Raw Materials Initiative; EU chemicals policy – REACH implementation; EU policies on recycling, sustainable use of resources, sustainable consumption and production; EU trade policy and trade defence actions.

INTERNATIONAL ASSOCIATION OF OIL AND GAS PRODUCERS – IOGP; *Industry sectors: ENERGY, OIL & GAS*

IOGP members produce more than a third of the world's oil and gas. They operate in all producing regions: the Americas, Africa, Europe, the Middle East, the Caspian, Asia and Australia. IOGP serves industry regulators as a global partner for improving safety, environmental and social performance. IOGP is dedicated to identifying and spreading good environmental practices wherever the upstream industry operates. Its work includes: ensuring continued access to new and known hydrocarbon sources; environmental management and reporting; gaseous emissions management; monitoring regulatory developments and developing advocacy positions.

EUROPEAN REMOTE SENSING INDUSTRY ASSOCIATION – EARSC; *Industry sectors: EARTH OBSERVATION REMOTE SENSING*

The European Association of Remote Sensing Companies (EARSC) is an industrial body that aims to foster the growth of the Earth observation (EO) services sector. Based in Brussels, EARSC coordinates and strengthens the EO chain and promotes the European geoinformation industry. The 74 full members of EARSC are companies supplying services in the growing market for the exploitation of EO data. Their main

activities are acquiring and supplying data from satellite or airborne platforms and /or their conversion into geo-information products suitable and accessible for their clients.

EUROPEAN SATELLITE APPLICATIONS INDUSTRY ASSOCIATION – EURISY; Industry sectors: SATELLITE APPLICATIONS (multisectoral)

The mission of Eurisy is to raise awareness of emerging satellite application advances and solutions taking place in numerous areas, from transport to risk management, from habitat protection to energy, and climate change. Eurisy's members include most Space Agencies and governmental offices in charge of space affairs in Europe, and international organisations dealing with space matters. Based on its direct fieldwork with end-users, Eurisy provides feedback to decision-makers on possible measures to overcome obstacles to the diffusion of space-derived innovation in society.

- b. Industrial suppliers: Most often, these are found in networks or clusters that may be reached through national ILOs. The clusters may offer an RI in-depth knowledge about their member and activities.
- c. Industrial collaborators: Potential RI industry partners engaged in technologies of interest for RIs, for example, big data processes and AI. These companies are natural allies of RIs in building, e.g., technical competence centres, data management/open data access, and semantic technologies to exploit and enrich research data.
- d. Industrial users: The industry in this group mainly acts as users of the RI facilities, services and data, for early-stage applied industrial research and for testing innovative developments and products. Additionally, the industry uses RI for training within the framework of exchange programmes. In this respect, the access to RI by PS is regulated by the “European Charter for Access to Research Infrastructures - Principles and Guidelines for Access and Related Services”: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/78e87306-48bc-11e6-9c64-01aa75ed71a1/>).

(b) to (c) may be found in the Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs) that operate in the space between the academic world and companies. The RTOs may be very different; some run a sustainable business primarily based on commercial work (e.g., testing, certification and consultancy) for companies or public institutions, while others perform R&D supported by public or regional funding. During the EPOS SP project, we have already contacted two RTOs: POLE AVENIA during GEOFEV DAYS and TWI LTD - Cambridge. POLE AVENIA is a competitiveness hub for the subsurface industries. Based in Pau in southwest France, AVENIA represents, oversees and federates 215 members (major groups, SMEs, research & training organizations, incentive and federative bodies). AVENIA knows and

understands all its members, and for this reason, is able to propose pertinent collective actions, boost the development and growth of its member companies, support them in their strategies and initiate innovative and collaborative R&D projects.

TWI Ltd – Cambridge is a membership-based organisation, supporting both individuals and companies alike. TWI exists to provide authoritative and impartial expert advice, know-how and safety assurance through engineering, materials and joining technologies – helping design, create and operate the best products possible. Descended from the British Welding Research Association (BWRA), TWI Ltd - Cambridge has grown into one of the foremost independent research and technology organisations. It spans innovation, knowledge transfer and problem resolution across all aspects of welding, joining, surface engineering, inspection and whole-life integrity management.

We recommend establishing contacts formally with at least these two RTOs through the MoU.

Appendix 1 - Main recommendations from ESFRI [ESFRI Scripta Vol. 2: Long-Term Sustainability of Research Infrastructures 2017]

The main recommendations that could ensure the long-term sustainability of RI are the following:

1. Ensuring scientific excellence through independent peer review, stable long-term funding critical for keeping the RI at the forefront of science, and maintaining RI's attractiveness both as service providers and as employers.
2. Managing tomorrow's RI through developing managerial skills of the RI's managers, by developing RI's user skills & outreach by specific training for RI's users, including industry users, by improving working conditions' improvement and career perspectives.
3. Unlocking the innovation potential of RI by a change in the mindset of the communities involved in the innovation cycle (RI, Academia and Industry), by attracting the industry both as a supplier and as a user of RI through more effective processes such as the co-innovation approach, which would enable to maximise synergies between science and industry, address new markets, promote the commercial application of science and facilitate commercial exploitation of research findings.
4. Measuring the socio-economic impact of RI by assessing and evaluating such impacts throughout the life cycle of RI.
5. Exploiting better the data generated by the RI by taking responsibility for the Data Management dimension with specific reference to the data storage, curation, access, and re-use aspects, by implementing a more integrated and interoperable approach to the data challenge, keeping into account, whenever necessary, the ethical, privacy, security, and copyright and IPR constraints.
6. RI Life cycle – Upgrading by performing a landscape analysis, which is developed on a multi-level approach considering inputs from several stakeholders such as users, scientific advisory boards, industry, and funders.
7. RI Life cycle – Decommissioning by planning this phase including channelling the know-how and transferring data.
8. Ensuring sustainable governance of RI by establishing better synergies among national roadmaps and synchronizing them with the funding planning processes in the Member States. National processes would need to be inserted into a European strategy, reason for which the EC should take a greater role in monitoring, supporting and facilitating the whole exercise, and by further developing the instrument such as VAT exemption, extension of the ERIC applicability to EURATOM, to international consortia and to research networks.
9. Funding the construction and operation of RI by stimulating the promotion of the business models development, by encouraging industrial investment for products and services joint development and the fostering of new sources of funding, and by tax incentives for (private) investment as well as a wider awareness/ promotion of RI services.
10. Structuring the international dimension of RI by improving cooperation with strategic partners and stakeholders and promoting it with an effective and multi-channel